

ON THE OXIDISING POWER OF BLUE CHROMIUM PEROXIDE IN RELATION TO ITS PROBABLE COMPOSITION

By RAM CHANDRA RAI

The oxidation values of the ethereal blue chromium peroxide (in two stages) and decomposition product have been investigated and the probable formula of the chromium peroxide is suggested.

In an earlier publication Rai and Prakash (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1943, 18A, 1) have studied the kinetics of the decomposition of the blue chromium peroxide in various organic media. They have further shown (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1954, 275, 94) that the blue chromium peroxide on decomposition furnishes chromium³⁺-dichromate, $\text{Cr}_2(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7)_3$. This substance, when strongly ignited, furnishes chromic oxide, Cr_2O_3 . The theoretical ratio between Cr^{3+} -dichromate and chromic oxide is 1.23 and the ratios obtained lie between 1.22 and 1.26 for different preparations.

In the present communication the results on the oxidising power of the blue chromium peroxide in different stages are recorded so as to ascertain the probable composition of this blue peroxide.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of the Blue Chromium Peroxide

The different samples of the blue peroxide were obtained from the following three sets of reacting mixtures.

First set: A 5% potassium dichromate solution (25 c.c.) was mixed with 2N- H_2SO_4 (5 c.c.), and varying concentrations of H_2O_2 added; the blue peroxide in each case was extracted with 50 c.c. of ether.

Second set: A 4% chromic acid solution (25 c.c.) was mixed with varying concentrations of H_2O_2 , and the blue peroxide in each case was extracted with 50 c.c. of ether.

Third set: Varying concentrations of chromic acid were mixed with 5 c.c. of 3N- H_2O_2 , and the blue peroxide in each case was extracted with 50 c.c. of ether.

These reactants were kept in ice, before they were mixed.

Estimation of Total Chromium.—The blue chromium peroxide was prepared by mixing the reactants, as outlined above, and the ethereal layer was separated in a separating funnel. A complete separation of the ethereal layer from the aqueous layer was carefully effected. The ethereal blue peroxide was taken in a Jena glass bottle and kept in ice; 10 c.c. of this solution was pipetted out in a tared silica crucible, evaporated on a water-bath, ignited and weighed as Cr_2O_3 .

Oxidising Power.—The iodometric titration was conducted in two stages:

First stage: The ethereal blue peroxide (5 c.c.) was added to a neutral aqueous solution of potassium iodide; the liberated iodine was titrated against a standard sodium thiosulphate (N/9.65) solution using starch solution as indicator. At this stage of the titration the colour of the solution was not green, but yellow.

Second stage: On completion of the first stage, to the same reaction mixture was added 2N- H_2SO_4 (5 c.c.); the further quantity of iodine liberated was titrated against the same standard thiosulphate solution.

Oxidising Power of the Decomposed Product.—The blue ethereal peroxide (10 c.c.) was left in a 100 c.c. flask for the spontaneous slow decomposition, and when decomposed, the solution was made up to 100 c.c., 25 c.c. of which was pipetted out and added to KI solution, and acidified with H_2SO_4 (dil.). The liberated iodine was titrated against the same standard thiosulphate solution.

Oxidising Power of the Ethereal Layer after Decomposition of the Blue Peroxide.—The bottle containing the blue peroxide was left overnight; all the acid was decomposed and the ether was left. The latter (5 c.c.) was pipetted out in an acidified solution of potassium iodide and the liberated iodine was titrated against the same sodium thiosulphate solution. This liberation of iodine corresponded to the solubility of hydrogen peroxide in ether and was deducted from other readings, when the ratios of the various oxidation values were calculated.

Thus from these titrations, the oxidising power of the blue peroxide in two stages and also of the decomposition product and the ether containing hydrogen peroxide, were determined, and from these results the various ratios, indicated, in Tables I-III, were calculated.

TABLE I

First set mixture: 5% $K_2Cr_2O_7$ taken = 25 c.c. 2N- H_2SO_4 taken = 5 c.c. Ether = 50 c.c.

1.5N- H_2O_2 used.	Cr_2O_3 present in 10 c.c. of blue peroxide.	Hyp used in 1st. stage.	Hyp used in 2nd. stage.	10 c.c. of 10 c.c. of product.	10 c.c. of ether left.	Ratio $\frac{(c+d-f)}{b}$	Ratio $\frac{(c+d-f)}{e}$	Ratio d/e.	Ratio $\frac{(c-f)}{d}$
(a).	(b).	(c).	(d).	(e).	(f).	(g).	(h).	(i).	(j).
2 c.c.	0.0016 g.	2.0 c.c.	2.9 c.c.	2.2 c.c.	0.5 c.c.	2750	2.00	1.32	0.51
4	0.0038	1.9	2.9	2.2	0.3	1158	2.04	1.32	0.51
6	0.0104	5.9	9.3	7.0	0.7	1394	2.07	1.32	0.55
8	0.0142	7.2	11.6	8.8	0.5	1289	2.08	1.32	0.57
10	0.0216	12.8	18.4	14.35	0.6	1417	2.01	1.29	0.65
12	0.0292	15.8	23.4	18.30	0.6	1322	2.10	1.29	0.64
14	0.0178	9.4	14.4	10.75	0.6	1303	2.15	1.34	0.61
16	0.0312	18.2	28.2	21.25	0.5	1471	2.16	1.30	0.62
18	0.0496	26.7	44.1	34.10	0.5	1417	2.06	1.29	0.58

TABLE II

Second set mixture: 4% Chromic acid taken = 25 c.c. Ether taken = 50 c.c.

3N- H_2O_2 used.	Cr_2O_3 present in 10 c.c. of blue peroxide.	Hyp used in 1st. stage.	Hyp used in 2nd. stage.	10 c.c. of 10 c.c. of product.	10 c.c. of ether left.	Ratio $\frac{(c+d-f)}{b}$	Ratio $\frac{(c+d-f)}{e}$	Ratio d/e.	Ratio $\frac{(c-f)}{d}$
(a)	(b)	(c)	(d)	(e)	(f)	(g)	(h)	(i)	(j)
2 c.c.	0.0038 g.	1.8 c.c.	3.0 c.c.	2.2 c.c.	0.4 c.c.	1157	2.00	1.36	0.46
4	0.0072	3.9	6.4	4.9	0.4	1375	2.02	1.32	0.50
6	0.0088	5.6	8.8	6.7	0.6	1568	2.06	1.33	0.57
8	0.0100	6.1	9.8	7.4	0.4	1550	2.09	1.33	0.58
10	0.0171	10.1	15.8	12.1	0.6	1479	2.08	1.305	0.56
12	0.0255	16.0	24.2	18.2	0.5	1557	2.17	1.33	0.64
14	0.0232	14.2	22.5	17.25	0.6	1556	2.06	1.29	0.56
16	0.0402	23.2	37.2	27.3	0.6	1487	2.20	1.36	0.59

TABLE III

Third set mixture : 3N-H₂O₂ taken = 5 c.c. Ether taken = 50 c.c.

4% Chromic acid used.	Cr ₂ O ₃ present in 10 c.c. of the blue peroxide.	Hypo 1st. stage.	used in 2nd. stage.	titrating 10 c.c. of decomp. product.	10 c.c. of ether left.	Ratio $\frac{(c+d-f)}{d}$.	Ratio $\frac{(c+d-f)}{e}$.	Ratio d/e.	Ratio $\frac{(c-f)}{d}$.
(a)	(b)	(c)	(d)	(e)	(f)	(g)	(h)	(i)	(j)
2 c.c.	0.0032 g.	1.5 c.c.	2.3 c.c.	1.5 c.c.	0.4 c.c.	1062	2.20	1.50	0.48
5	0.0056	2.2	3.4	2.3	0.7	875	2.10	1.45	0.45
10	0.0178	6.2	10.1	7.6	0.7	876	2.03	1.33	0.54
15	0.0178	6.1	10.0	7.65	0.6	871	2.04	1.30	0.55
20	0.0258	9.1	14.4	10.9	0.6	886	2.09	1.32	0.59
25	0.0260	9.3	14.7	11.3	0.4	908	2.09	1.30	0.60
30	0.0170	6.0	9.1	7.0	0.4	864	2.07	1.30	0.59
40	0.0128	5.0	8.2	6.15	0.4	1000	2.08	1.33	0.53
50	0.0176	5.7	9.0	7.1	0.4	812	2.01	1.26	0.58

DISCUSSION

The following observations are made from the results recorded in Tables I, II and III.

(i) The amount of available oxygen from different samples of the blue peroxide is very nearly proportional to the amount of Cr³⁺-oxide (Cr₂O₃) content. The ratios shown in the column (g) lie between 1.3 and 1.5 × 10³ (Tables I and II); the values are, however, lower in Table III, ranging from 850 to 1000. The fluctuations are either due to the variations in the distribution of hydrogen peroxide in aqueous and ether layers or to the fact that the blue peroxide is not always of a definite composition.

(ii) The ratio between the total oxidising power of the blue peroxide and the oxidising value of the decomposition product obtained from the same quantity of the blue peroxide is very nearly 2 : 1 (column h). We have shown in the previous publication (*loc. cit.*) that this "decomposition product" has the composition of chromium dichromate, Cr₂(Cr₂O₇)₃. This ratio is significant in deciding the composition of the blue peroxide.

(iii) The ratio between the oxidation value of the second stage titration of the blue peroxide and the "decomposition product" obtained from the same volume of the blue peroxide is near about 1.33, as seen from the column (i) of the three tables.

(iv) The ratio between the oxidation values in the "first" and "second" stage titrations lies between 0.5 and 0.6, as seen from the column (j) of the three tables.

Schwarz and Giess and their collaborators (*Ber.*, 1932, 65, 871; 1933, 66B, 330; Schwarz and Elstner, *Ber.*, 1936, 69, 575; see also Rosenheim, Hakki and Krause, *Z.*

anorg. Chem., 1932, 209, 175) have ascribed the formula CrO_5 to the blue peroxide. Our view is that the peroxide is of an indefinite composition, which only as its higher limits may show this composition. Ordinarily it corresponds to the composition $\text{CrO}_{3.75}$ or Cr_8O_{30} . Since on its spontaneous decomposition it furnishes chromium dichromate, during its reactivity it shows the following equilibrium :

This for convenience, we may term chromium perchromate.

In the "first stage" of the iodimetric titrations (in absence of acids) the decomposition proceeds to

In the "second stage" of iodimetric titration, the decomposition proceeds to the final chromium oxide :

We have already stated that on the spontaneous decomposition of the blue peroxide, chromium dichromate is obtained which is a water-soluble substance and which has the oxidation power similar to other dichromates :

The ratio of the available oxygen from equations (i) and (ii) is 1:2, as shown in column (j) ; the ratio of the available oxygen from equations (ii) and (iii) is 12:9 or 1:1.33, as shown in column (i). The ratio between the total oxygen from equations (i) and (ii), taken together, and the equation (iii) is 18:9 or 2:1, as shown in column (h).

If the blue chromium peroxide be regarded to have at some stage the composition of chromium 'perchromate', $\text{Cr}_2(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_{10})_3$, the decomposition product "chromium dichromate" is attained through the following stages :

In case the blue peroxide is assumed to be of the composition CrO_5 , as proposed by other workers, the various stages of the decomposition would be as follows :

This mechanism would demand the ratio between the total available oxygen and the oxygen available from chromium dichromate to be 28:9, i.e., 3.1:1 ; whereas our ratios in column (h) indicate it to be near about 2:1. This leads to the view that the blue chromium peroxide has a composition something like $\text{CrO}_{3.75}$ or rather Cr_8O_{30} , and not CrO_5 .

Thanks of the author are due to Dr. Satya Prakash, D.Sc., F.A.Sc. for his kind interest in the work.